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Efficacy of a Sensory Re-Education Paradigm on Postural Stability in Chemotherapy-Induced Peripheral Neuropathy Among Breast Cancer Survivors: A Randomized Controlled Trial (RCT)

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Abstract

Background: Worldwide, breast cancer is the most common type of cancer. Among females, it's the main cause of cancer death. Chemotherapy-induced peripheral neuropathy (CIPN) is a prevalent serious side effect deriving from neurotoxic chemotherapeutic agents and a limiting factor in using them. The underlying nerve injury can affect proprioception and foot sensitivity causing impaired postural control. Sensory re-education is a therapeutic rehabilitation program that uses repeated sensory stimulation to recover functional sensibility in the affected area and learn adaptive functioning.**Purpose:** to study the effect of sensory re-education paradigm on postural stability in patient with CIPN.**Methodology:** Thirty CIPN female patients were randomly assigned in two equal groups. The control group (A) received a selected physical therapy program for 18 sessions. The study group (B) received the same physical therapy program in addition to a designed sensory re-education program for 18 sessions every other day. Pre- and post-treatment assessment were performed using Biodex balance system and Semmes-Weinstein monofilament.**Results:** There was a statistically significant improvement in feet sensitivity and postural stability parameters in both groups in favor of the study group.**Conclusion:** The designed sensory re-education paradigm has improved postural stability and foot sensation significantly in survived breast-cancer females with CIPN.

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KeyWords:Breast cancer, Chemotherapy-induced peripheral neuropathy, Postural stability, Sensory re-education.

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The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

Introduction

The most common type of cancer among females all over the world is breast cancer. Breast cancer is considered a leading cause for cancer death among females. Recently more accurate and new therapies have improved the survival rate (**Sung et al., 2021**). Classical antitumoral drugs are cytotoxic that inhibit cancer cell division. Chemotherapy induced peripheral neurotoxicity (CIPN) is a predominantly sensory neuropathy usually first reported in the lower limbs that may be accompanied by motor and autonomic changes (**Cavaletti et al., 2019**).

CIPN is reported to affect over 70 % of patients more than six months after completing neurotoxic chemotherapy treatment (**Battaglini et al., 2021**). The clinical picture is characterized by symptoms such as tingling, numbness, burning and/or pain in hands and/or feet, reduced or absent Achilles tendon reflexes, pain, and loss of balance control (**Kneis et al., 2016**).

Impairments in foot sensitivity such as reduced tactile sensation have been linked to postural instability and gait changes that may potentially increase the risk of falls (**Ueda & Carpes, 2013; Croarkin et al., 2015**). Consequently, CIPN can also lead to unstable gait, as well as an increased incidence of accidents and falls (**Winters-Stone et al 2017**).

For these reasons, motor deficits including balance impairment, lower gait speed and lower limb strength are also recurring, with an increased falling frequency (**Niederer et al., 2014**). Moreover, the postural control shows clinical meaningful impairments, and as a vicious circle, gait speed is also negatively affected due to a decrease in physical exercise participation with a framework of general physical deconditioning. These deficits, associated with an increased fear of falling, may limit patients' independence (**Schwenk et al., 2016**).

Sensory re-education is a therapeutic rehabilitation program that uses repeated sensory stimulation to help sensory impaired patients recover functional sensibility in the affected area and learn adaptive functioning (**Odeyoyin & Shilpa, 2019**). The focus of sensory re-education is to retrain the patient to use what residual function remains (**Robinson & Shannon, 2002**). Clinical studies on exercise yielded some promising results in CIPN especially for balance and fitness outcomes, although

empirical evidence on its efficacy is still insufficient (**Kanzawa et al., 2020; Lin et al., 2021**).

Intermittent pneumatic compression (IPC) therapy can produce a kind of circulating pressure that acts on the limbs and tissues through repeated air inflation and deflation to the air bag in an ordered and regular manner, which can promote the flow of blood and lymph, and improve the microcirculation. IPC therapy is mainly used for the prevention of deep vein thrombosis of the lower limbs (**Jiang et al, 2018**).

Among the goals of sensory re-education, one is to retrain neural pathways and responses to stimuli in order to restore patient's sensory perception (**Chick G, 2013**). Increased sensory input and activity may help to stimulate nerve regeneration and growth. In addition, previously unused neural connections may be trained to take over for damaged pathways. This neural plasticity can be used to the advantage of a patient with nerve damage or impairment (**Al-Shahry et al, 2020**).

Subjects and Methods

Design:

A randomized control trial was conducted to investigate the impact of sensory re-education paradigm on postural stability in patient with Chemotherapy-induced peripheral neuropathy. Data were collected pre and post treatment from out-patient clinic of the Faculty of Medicine and Faculty of Physical Therapy South Valley University, between March 2020 and March 2022. The study was approved by the ethical committee of the Faculty of Physical Therapy, Cairo University, Egypt. The study protocol was explained in detail to every patient and a signed written consent was obtained before participation.

Participants:

Thirty female patients with CIPN were recruited from out-patient clinic of the Faculty of Medicine and Faculty of Physical Therapy South Valley University, between March 2020 and March 2022.

Inclusion criteria:

Thirty female patients (age from 35-60 years) clinically diagnosed with CIPN after recovery from stage I or II breast cancer followed by chemotherapy and suffer from significant sensory loss. Ankle, knee, and hip range of motion are within normal limits. The strength at the toes,

ankles, knees, and hips, as determined by manual muscle tests, of at least 3/5. The patients can walk independently with or without any assistive devices. They can also stand unassisted for 5 min.

Exclusion criteria:

Patient who had any of the following problems were excluded: patients with a history of peripheral neuropathy (i.e., hereditary peripheral neuropathy associated with nutritional agents and paraneoplastic), diseases that may contribute to peripheral nerve damage, such as diabetes or renal insufficiency, alcohol abuse, HIV, and vasculitis. Any patient who had central or peripheral neurologic disease, brain or spinal cord metastases, orthopedic problems influencing gait, or foot ulcer at the moment of intake. Patients with vestibular problem or neurological problems influencing gait parameters or those patients who had corrected low-contrast visual acuity worse than 20/60 and a corrected high-contrast visual acuity worse than 20/40 were also excluded. Finally, subjects who had participated in regular exercise, as defined as 150 min of light-to-moderate intensity exercise per week over the past year, were excluded from this trial.

Randomization:

The recruited patients were randomized by sealed, opaque, identical envelopes into two groups: group (A) and group (B). Each patient drew an envelope containing the group she was in, whether it was group (A) or (B). The number of patients in each group was 15. The anonymity and confidentiality of each patient was assured.

Evaluation Procedures:

All patients were evaluated pre- and post-treatment using:

1-Semmes-Weinstein monofilament (SWM):

The short version (pocket filaments) with five filaments from 0.07 to 300 g were used (Touch Test® Sensory Evaluators, North Coast Medical Inc.). The assessment was conducted in a quiet setting and subjects were instructed to close their eyes during the test. First, the monofilament was applied to the subject's forearm, and they were asked about the feeling and location of the test to ensure the subject's understanding. All subjects were tested at nine regions of the foot as fig (1). Subjects were asked to name the exact location where a monofilament was detected. If subjects perceived the test

location correctly 2 out of 3 times, the subject's sensory score was noted as intact (**Da Silva Simão, 2014**).

While testing, proceed from distal to proximal and from small to large monofilaments. Checks may be done over areas innervated by different nerves. The filament was placed at a 90° angle and pushed against the skin until it bent and was held in place for 1.5 seconds and then removed. For monofilaments from 1.65 to 4.08, the stimulus was applied in the same location up to three times to elicit a response and a single response indicated a positive response. For filaments 4.17 through 6.65, the stimulus was applied one time only. Testing results were recorded using a colored pencil that corresponds to the color on the handle of the monofilament used. The size of each monofilament was noted and recorded in order to evaluate the touch detection thresholds of the foot and toes (**Akahori et al, 2004**). Touch detection threshold was scored on a 0 to 5-point scale, where 5 represents the thinnest filament and 0 represents the largest filament.

- 0 = not testable
- 1 = filament 6.65 (magenta 300g)
- 2 = filament 4.56 (red 4g)
- 3 = filament 4.31 (violet 2.0g)
- 4 = filament 3.61 (blue 0.4g)
- 5 = filament 2.83 (green 0.07g)

(Paula et al., 2016)

Fig (1). Nine touch sites per foot (seven plantar and two dorsal) in SWM test (Adapted from Akahori et al, 2004)

2- Biodex balance system SD as an objective assessment device for postural stability.

In this study postural stability was measured using a Biodex Balance System SD (950-440 with version 4.X software) which is an instrument designed to measure and train the postural stability on a static or unstable surface. The Biodex Balance System (BBS) consists of a mobile platform with 20 degrees of tilt in all directions and

12 levels of difficulty. The Stability Index of the Biodex Balance System (SI-BBS) has been used in studies assessing postural stability. Emphasizes a patient's ability to maintain center of balance. The BBS calculates, F/B stability, L/R stability, F/B sway, L/R sway, Overall sway index and overall stability index (OSI), showing the degree of tilt about the AP and ML axes. The patient's score on this test assesses deviations from center, thus a lower score is more desirable than a higher score. Performing a postural stability test:

1. Position the support handles and the display height and tilt for patient comfort.
2. On patient setup information screen, the patient's name and height must be entered.
3. Here the test trial time can be set, the sensory conditions to be tested can be selected, the number of trials can be entered, and the rest countdown time (i.e., the time between trials) can be entered. Set to default of the device.
4. Platform stability can be varied, to set Initial or Ending Platform Stability (static, 1 is the next most stable, 12 is least stable,). In this study, initial was static and ending was at level 4.
5. To have either the cursor or tracing biofeedback displayed during the test, touch the checkboxes next to the options.
6. In the position patient screen, the dot on it represents the patient's center of gravity. Have the patient stand in a natural stance, slightly adjusting foot placement until the dot is on or close to the center axis. Then, enter the patient's left foot, left heel, right foot and right heel positions using the midline of the foot and the platform grid as reference points.
7. If desired, show tracing or remove any tracing, press on "show tracing" icon (the left-most icon under tracing) or press the clear tracing icon for remove any tracing that is left from a previous training session.
8. Press start icon to activate the postural stability test screen.
9. With the patient ready to begin the test, touch "collect data" icon. The screen will provide a three-second countdown before beginning the first of three test trials. The display screen will include the trial time and platform setting. Trial number and score are displayed. If desired, touch the Magnifying Glass icon to enlarge the grid circle.

10. When the first trial is finished, the screen will display "Trial 1 Complete," the platform will return to the locked position, and a rest countdown will begin for the second trial. Touch Collect Data icon to begin the second test trial and continue in the same manner to complete subsequent trials.

11. After completing the test, a "Test Complete" message is displayed. Touch Results icon to advance to the Postural Stability Test Results screen.

12. Here in, you can print or save results by touching their icons (**Recktenwald, 2021**).

Treatment Procedures:

Both groups received three sessions per week for six weeks. The duration of each session was approximately one hour. Treatment program was as follows:

I) Control group: (Group A):

This group consists of 15 patients with CIPN which treated by a selected physical therapy program only. The program consisted of (core exercises, AROM exercises, and stretching exercises for LL for 18 sessions every other day, over 6 weeks (**Colberg et al., 2010**).

II) Study Group (Group B):

This group received the designed sensory re-education paradigm 3 times a week, over 6 weeks in addition to the same selected physical therapy program for 18 sessions every other day. The program included the following exercises:

1-Sensory cuing therapy through vision and auditory.

Sensory re-education is based on cortical plasticity with remapping of the cortex by experience and defined as the gradual and progressive process of reprogramming the brain using cognitive learning techniques such as visualization and verbalization, the use of alternate senses such as vision or hearing and the use of graded tactile stimuli designed to restore sensory areas affected by nerve injury (**Novak & Christine, 2011**). Sensory rehabilitation is considered one of the challenges and a persistent functional deficit in the long term. All rehabilitation paradigms use re-education in many different ways. The main issue here is that the brain mostly recognizes, considers and reacts with structured, and consistent input (**Al-Shahry et al, 2020**).

2-Gradual Intermittent pneumatic compression therapy (IPC): therapeutic apparatus (Lympha Pro UAM-8400 MAXSTAR industrial Co., Ltd) was adopted for treatment. Patients were asked to lie in supine position and chambers' inflatable air bladders leg cuffs of IPC placed around their feet to the upper part of thigh. One cuff was secured to each leg. When the system was active, the bladders rapidly inflated and deflated (within ~30 sec) sequentially in a peristaltic manner from feet to the upper part of thigh, and the mode was selected according to patients' conditions. The pressure was adjusted from bottom to top based on patients' tolerance ranging from 30 mmHg to 60 mmHg (1 mmHg = 0.133 kPa), trying to reduce the discomfort and maximize the curative effect. The treatment was conducted for 20 min/time (Jiang et al., 2018).

3-Additional balance exercise using protocol training ball methodRojhani-Shirazi (2016) was combined with the movement from the fall prevention center of excellence at California State University. The exercises were practiced in groups and in two positions, that were sitting (in the chair and Swiss ball) and standing. Exercise in the sitting position: (patient with CIPN had to sit upright and move their ankle in opening and closing direction, lift the forefoot but maintain the heel to be attached, lift the leg at the same time to be in line with the thigh, sit upright and hold the ball with both hands then move the hands over and above the head, rotate the body to the left and right, cross the body bent from the top right side to the lower left side (do the opposite), sit and pass the ball with the hands and feet). Exercises in standing positions: (patient with CIPN had to exercise tandem standing and walking , semi-tandem standing, and walking, pass the ball with both hands while walking , pass the ball with both hands from over the head and from the bottom between the legs ,pass the ball with the legs) .

4-Proprioceptive neuromuscular facilitation (PNF) technique: The second LE diagonal (D2) pattern consists of hip Flexion/Abduction/Internal Rotation was used. The leg begins in hip and knee extension with external rotation of the hip. In order to position the knee past the midline of the body, the leg not involved in the pattern is abducted. The foot is plantar flexed and inverted. The patient is requested to "pull your foot up and out" (Martin et al., 2007).

Statistical analysis:

The statistical analysis was conducted by using Statistical package for the social sciences computer program (version 20 for Windows; SPSS Inc., Chicago, Illinois, USA), and were expressed the mean ± standard deviation (SD) or percentage (%). For normality investigation, the Shapiro–Wilks test was used for numerical data, and the Chi-square test (χ^2) was used for categorical data. Data of the SWM, Overall stability index, Overall sway index, F/B stability, L/R stability, F/B sway and L/R sway were analyzed by Student's t test to compare between subjects' demographic data of the two groups. one-way ANOVA was performed to compare within and between groups' effects for all measured variables. A p value < 0.05 was considered significant.

Results

In this study, a total of thirty patients were included, and divided randomly in two groups: control group (A) and study group (B). Fig (2).

Fig (2). Flow Diagram of the study

-Characteristics of subjects in both groups: (Table 1)

There were no significant differences in clinical characteristic between both groups (A&B) concerning age (years), weight (Kg), height (cm) and BMI (kg/m²) (p> 0.05).

Table (1): Characteristics of Patients in Both Groups:

Measured variables	Group A Mean±SD	Group B Mean±SD	t-value	p-value
Age (years)	40.8±3.6	42.5±5.1	-0.698	0.500
Weight (kg)	80.5±3.8	82.1±3.4	-0.821	0.429
Height (cm)	162.3±3	162.9±2.4	-0.349	0.734
BMI (kg/m ²)	30.2±0.8	31±1.1	-1.435	0.179

-Postural stability parameter measured by Biodex Balance System: Table (2)

There was a statistically significant improvement in all postural stability parameter in both groups after treatment, with favor of the study group.

Table (2): Comparison between pre- and post-study mean values of balance measuring among groups.

Balance	Pre-study Mean ±SD	Post-study Mean ±SD	% of change	P value
Overall stability index				
Group A	1.8 ± 0.1	1.6 ± 0.08	11.1%	0.031*
Group B	1.7 ± 0.15	1.3 ± 0.19	23.5%	0.001*
(P-value)	0.108	0.002*		
Overall sway index				
Group A	1.7 ± 0.13	1.6 ± 0.12	6%	0.084
Group B	1.7 ± 0.1	1.47 ± 0.07	13.5%	0.001*
(P-value)	0.586	0.009*		
F/B stability				
Group A	0.9 ± 0.14	0.75 ± 0.15	16.7%	0.085
Group B	0.87 ± 0.15	0.48 ± 0.13	44.8%	0.001*
(P-value)	0.725	0.003*		
F/B sway				
Group A	1.05 ± 0.09	0.89 ± 0.06	15.2%	0.008*
Group B	0.95 ± 0.12	0.64 ± 0.12	32.6%	0.001*
(P-value)	0.081	0.001*		
L/R stability				
Group A	0.96 ± 0.12	0.8 ± 0.15	16.7%	0.038*
Group B	0.93 ± 0.14	0.61 ± 0.11	34.4%	0.001*
(P-value)	0.606	0.018*		
L/R sway				
Group A	0.83 ± 0.1	0.61 ± 0.16	26.5%	0.004*
Group B	0.77 ± 0.11	0.39 ± 0.07	49.3%	0.001*
(P-value)	0.428	0.002*		

-Sensory threshold of the affected feet measured by Semmes-Weinstein monofilament (SWM) test: Table (3)

There was a statistically significant improvement in the feet sensitivity in both groups after treatment, but in favor of the study group, a superior improvement was achieved.

Table (3): Comparison between pre- and post-study mean values of SWM among groups.

SWM	Pre-study Mean ±SD	Post-study Mean ±SD	% of change	P value
Group A	48.7 ± 8.2	56.3 ± 6	15.6%	0.041*
Group B	45.7 ± 4.8	65.1 ± 5.3	42.5%	0.001*
(P-value)	0.394	0.017*		

Discussion

The current study aimed to spotlight the efficacy of sensory re-education paradigm on postural stability after chemotherapy-induced neuropathy. In respect to the study group which received SR paradigm in addition to the selected therapeutic exercise program, there was superiority in improvement of sensibility threshold, postural control, that gives this paradigm of Sensory re-education an additional

superiority over the selected therapeutic program since some postural control statistically non-significant.

In this randomized controlled clinical trial, significant improvement of the feet sensitivity in the study group who received a selected designed SR program than control group. These results agreed with Müller et al (2021) reported that subjectively perceived sensory symptoms in the feet increased less during chemotherapy in the adherent exercisers (pooled group: SMT+RT) compared to usual care group. A decrease in PNP symptoms was detected also in another study, which indicated a reduction of 98% in particular in the “Abnormally sensitive to touch”, after 10 weeks of exercise training (Wonders et al., 2013).

Also, the results of this study agreed with Yousuf et al (2020a) who postulated that adding sensory re-education paradigm to traditional physical therapy is a beneficial rehabilitation program in improving the functional outcomes in patients with CTS.

Similarly, these results agreed with Bland et al. (2019) showing improvement of foot/toe numbness and vibration sense after 10 weeks of supervised aerobic, resistance and balance training 3 times per week. Also, Kneis et al. (2019) showed improvement of overall and sensory symptoms without improvement of vibration sense and jump height after 12 weeks of endurance and balance training for intervention group. The improvement of hot/coldness and improvement of numbness and tingling was detected also in Kleckner et al. (2018) after 6 weeks with daily Walking and resistance training.

Recent study in contrast with our results from Winberg et al (2021) comparing foot sensation pre- to post intermittent pneumatic compression resulted in no statistical differences regardless of the tested site. According to Mizrahi et al. (2015) there were no significant differences in the Functional Assessment Cancer Therapy-Neurotoxicity (FACT Neurotoxicity), a scale used to assess chemotherapy-induced neurological symptoms (Huang et al., 2007). Also, Zimmer et al. (2018) showed the neuropathic symptoms remained stable while they worsened in the control group after 8 weeks of endurance, resistance, and balance training for 2 times per week.

The significant improvement of response to a touching sensation revealed by the monofilaments

in the study group is induced by the increase in nerve blood supply by applying IPC. This is a possible cause and we do not have direct measurement of blood flow in this study. In this context, (IPC) of the lower legs has been shown to increase blood flow to the lower limbs (**Gibbons et al., 2019; Zuj et al., 2019, 2021**), and therefore may be another appropriate modality for improving CIPN symptoms. Also, according to **Delis et al (2005)** that a probable mechanism for enhancement of the arterial inflow in the legs seems to be an increase in the hydrostatic pressure gradient.

In the current study, also, light touch sensation demonstrated significant changes after IPC therapy. The possible cause of significant results of light touch sensation may be innervations overlap of the plantar surface of foot. **McBride et al (1982)** indicated that highly specialized mechanoreceptors responsible for light touch sensitivity, the Meissner corpuscles and Merkel cell neurite complexes, are densely located in the glabrous skin of the palm and fingertips. Several receptors are activated by a weak tactile stimulus. However, extensive overlap in peripheral innervations of receptive fields does not let the pathologic conditions in a moderate number of nerve fibers greatly change tactile discrimination capability.

Additionally, a large overlap of innervations was seen between sensory nerve fibers and receptive fields. A possible mechanism of IPC for improvement in light touch sensation may be reduction in edema involving the nerves. In other words, it is probable that exerting an intermittent external pressure on lower limbs of CIPN patients compresses the vessels leading to reduce edema induced by endothelial dysfunction and ischemia in these sensitive nerve fibers. These events enhance circulation and tissue perfusion while gradually retaining the normal function of nerves.

Previous studies, also introduced several treatment methods, such as Tai Chi and other exercises for improving results of functional stability tests in patients with DN. They postulated that improvements in plantar sensory perception contribute to better postural control, unipedal stance time, and tandem stance (**Ahn& Song, 2011**). A possible reason for these improvements may be the increase in release of nitric oxide secondary to exercise (**Koller et al ,1998**). Studies of **Tan et al (2006)** and **Chen et**

al (2002) also showed that applying IPC on the lower limbs of diabetic patients can regulate and increase the endothelial nitric oxide secretion. Comparing the results of this study with other researchers suggest that the increase in secretion of NO by applying IPC can stimulate vasodilation on microvascular system and probably enhance blood supply of the peripheral nervous system of the lower limb.

Although CIPN is considered a peripheral syndrome, some neuronal adaptations happen in the central nervous system. Central sensitization is neuronal adaptations happen in the central nervous system (**Woolf, 2007**). Central sensitization is a phenomenon where the neurons show the ability to adapt according to the stimuli being offered and this adaptation persists even after the peripheral stimuli is stopped (**Carlton et al., 2009**). Pain is the most commonly studied area when it comes to central sensitization processes. However, central sensitization may occur in different types of sensory receptors as well such as mechanoreceptors responsible for touch and pressure. Such adaptability is due to an imbalance between excitability and inhibition and may lead to abnormal (i.e., increased or reduced) responses (**Lima et al, 2018**).

Also, the significant improvement of response to the feet sensitivity of the monofilaments in the study group can be postulated to corrected afferent sensory input may lead to improvement in perceiving changes in an environment, such as ground and shoe unevenness (**Ueda and Carpes ,2013**). Also, with improving an abnormal functioning of the nervous system leading to improvement in planter forefoot and rearfoot peak pressure areas which improve muscle balance and improve proprioception as the greater the severity of neuropathy, the higher the peak pressure in those planter forefoot and rearfoot. additionally, functional shortening of the Achilles tendon and possible rupture of the plantar fascia in more severe stages of neuropathy may lead to such abnormal pressures in those areas (**Acharya et al., 2008; Caselli et al, 2002**).

So, the significant improvement of response to a touching sensation of the monofilaments in the study group in relation to the control group of the present study can be postulated to the application of sensory re-education paradigm that provides retrain neural pathways and responses to stimuli in order to restore patient's sensory perception (**Chick, 2013**). Increased sensory input and

activity may help to stimulate nerve regeneration and growth. In addition, previously unused neural connections may be trained to take over for damaged pathways. This neural plasticity can be used to the advantage of a patient with nerve damage or impairment (**Al-Shahry et al, 2020**).

The results of the current study revealed significant improvement in postural stability which was tested by The Biodex Balance System. This finding agrees with **Streckmann et al. (2014b)**, who measured sway paths during static monopodal stance through a force platform, showed an improvement in the IG by 18% with a concurrent decline in the CG.

On the contrary for static balance control, **Schwenk et al. (2016)**, using three wearable sensors, showed a reduction for the intervention group (IG) compared to the control group (CG) in Medio-Lateral Center of Mass (COM) sway (55.5%), hip sway (67.5%) and ankle sway (68.2%) during balance assessment with feet closed, and in Medio-Lateral COM sway (47.6%), Antero-Posterior COM sway (43.9%), and hip sway (74.8%) during evaluations in semitandem position.

Similarly, these results agreed with, **Yousuf et al (2020b)** who postulated that visual feedback training yields improvement in decreasing risk of falling in PD patients compared to sensory integration training.

Also, results of this study for dynamic balance control agreed with **Kneis et al. (2019)** showed improvement of reduced sway path (semi-tandem /monopodal on unstable surface). Recent study agreed with this study results **Winberg et al (2021)** which majority of cases reported that stride length was found to be unchanged following IPC, but stride velocity increased as overall Timed Up and Go duration decreased by a statistically significant amount (~7.0% or 1.05 s) following a single exposure to IPC

On the contrary for dynamic balance control **Schwenk et al, (2016)** investigated gait performance, using wearable sensors; postulated no significant changes were noted in both IG and CG and Falls Efficacy Scale-International version (FES-I score).

As CIPN patient showed combination of highest pressure in the fore-foot with a higher AP sway might be an indicative of the center of gravity for these individuals being placed anteriorly shifting their body slightly forward.

This combination may lead to postural instability potentially increasing the risk of falls According to **Lima et al (2018)** under the open eyes condition. Interestingly, these reductions in sway path as reduction in F/B sway and L/R sway indexes were observed in both the AP and ML planes, which shows potential robustness in control responses from muscles groups acting across multiple joints (e.g., hip flexors/extensors for AP control, ankle inverters/evertors and for ML control during tandem stance) (**Sozzi, et al, 2013; Winter et al, 1996**).

Also, with improvement of foot planter surface sensory threshold that improve sensory perception of high arc foot of CIPN according to **Lima et al (2018)** that in turn improve associated dysfunctions such as absent tendon reflexes, impaired dorsiflexion, and loss of sensitivity are crucial parameters for balance and gait. Therefore, the improvement of these parameters could potentially contribute to reduce disability and falls (**Streckmann et al ,2019**). The improvement of sensibility levels (SWM) and the improvement in Overall stability index, Overall sway index which could be an explanation for distributing more weight in the foot that offers the best sensory input.

With the limitations of this study, it could be concluded that sensory re-education paradigm is a beneficial therapeutic program in the rehabilitation of patients with CIPN. Adding this paradigm to the physical therapy program is beneficial in improving feet sensitivity and postural control.

Conclusion

In view of the results of this study, it could be concluded that sensory re- education paradigm improves the postural stability and feet sensitivity in patients with Chemotherapy-induced peripheral neuropathy who survived from breast cancer.

Conflict of interest

Authors declare no conflict of interest.

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